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Genome-informed design of LAMP assays for specific detection of aster yellows phytoplasmas

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Abstract

Genome sequence data is becoming more available and represents a source of potential target sequences for specific molecular tests to verify the feasibility and efficiency of genome-inform test design the attempt to identify novel specific sequences in the publicly available genomes of aster yellows phytoplasmas and use them to design primers for a specific LAMP assays. Coupling RUCS automated analysis with PrimerExplorer V5 primer designer and applying criteria for selection of assays at each stage of the process resulted in 13 promising LAMP assays targeting four newly identified regions specific to aster yellows phytoplasmas.

Keywords: molecular tests, genome data, aster yellows target sequences

Introduction

Research on biology and epidemiology of phytoplasmas relies on the ability to detect them. Since most phytoplasmas are difficult to culture, serological and molecular methods could be applied to detect and characterize them. Among the promising methods for detection of phytoplasmas is LAMP (loop mediated isothermal amplification), a molecular method generating high quantities of amplified DNA from a specific DNA fragment using a set of four to six primers (Notomi *et al.*, 2000). The advantages of this method include: isothermal amplification, speed and high resilience to various inhibitors present in the samples. These characteristics in turn allow detection of pathogenic bacteria, including phytoplasmas, on-site in the field with a minimal sample preparation (Kogovsek *et al.*, 2015; 2017). However, DNA sequences most commonly used for detection of phytoplasmas are often not suitable targets for LAMP which requires 4-6 primers with specific characteristics. To expand the range of potential target sequences of LAMP an exploitation of available genomic data of various phytoplasmas was performed to identify potential novel sequences specific to the phytoplasma subgroups of interest. As a test case attempt to identify and design LAMP assays against aster yellows phytoplasmas were done.

Materials and Methods

Two publicly available genomes of aster yellows phytoplasma (complete genome of aster yellows witches' broom

phytoplasma AYWB, Accession number CP000061.1; draft genome of New Jersey aster yellows phytoplasma strain NJAY, Accession number MAPF01000000) were selected as target. The specific sequences were identified through comparison of the target genomes with a set of 70 non-target including 15 phytoplasmas genomes (5 closed) and 55 genomes of mycoplasma (22 closed). An automated analysis using previously described and freely available pipelines, namely "find differential primers" (Pritchard *et al.*, 2012) and RUCS (Thomsen *et al.*, 2017), was used to identify target unique sequences of aster yellows phytoplasmas. In the second step, the specific sequences were filtered based on pre-defined characteristics required for the LAMP design and used to design LAMP primer sets using PrimerExplorer V5 (<http://primerexplorer.jp/lampv5e/index.html>) and LAMP Designer (<http://www.optigene.co.uk/lamp-designer/>). The proposed primers were further inspected *in silico* for the most relevant properties related to their expected performance including specificity assessment using BLASTn, leading to a selection of the most promising LAMP assays.

Results

Of the two pipelines used to identify unique sequences in the aster yellows genomes, the RUCS pipeline was found to be more suitable. Compared to the pipeline "find differential primers" it was easier to install and use, and required no adaptation (artificial closing) of draft genomes before

analysis. In addition, it is web based, and identifies unique sequences of various sizes. Applying RUCS to the selected 72 genomes resulted in identification of 5,139 sequences unique for the aster yellows genome. The majority of these sequences (97%) was 199 nucleotides long or less. In the range most suitable for the LAMP design *i.e.* 300-600 nucleotides, 137 sequences were identified. The unique sequences of all lengths were distributed throughout the aster yellows genome. In total, 150 of the longest unique sequences were further examined for their specificity using BLAST program. Sequences with similarities to partially sequenced phytoplasma genomes, common bacterial species or phytoplasma hosts were excluded. Out of the remaining 57 specific sequences, 10 longest sequences with mostly unknown function were used for the LAMP primer design (Table 1).

Table 1. Sequences unique for aster yellows phytoplasmas as identified with RUCS and the number of the accepted LAMP assays.

Sequence	Position ^a	Length (nucleotides)	Average % GC	LAMP assays ^b
Seq1	402,284	1,946	27%	0
Seq2	44,205	1,981	26%	2
Seq3	667,186	1,972	23%	6
Seq4	404,906	1,581	22%	0
Seq5	46,673	1,241	19%	0
Seq6	266,394	1,083	21%	0
Seq7	692,620	1,080	20%	0
Seq8	112,041	1,045	22%	0
Seq9	397,407	985	26%	5
Seq10	255,325	932	29%	0

^astart position of sequence in the complete genome of onion aster yellows phytoplasma.

^btotal number of LAMP assays which passed the quality control analysis.

Both softwares applied for designing the LAMP primer sets were found to be easy to use, adaptable and gave comparable results in the preliminary test. However, PrimerExplorer V5 was selected for final design because it is freely available. When necessary, the stringency of the primer design parameters was modified to allow primer design. Default parameters were modified for AT rich sequences with length of F2/B2 and F3/B3 primer pair increased to 15-25 bp and GC percentage lowered to 25-65%. The proposed LAMP assays were checked manually and filtered using pre-defined criteria: free energy of primer dimers, positioning in different parts of target sequences, quality of 5' primer ends and their melting temperature. Finally, assays were further checked for primer specificity using BLASTn algorithm. LAMP primers considered of sufficient quality were successfully designed on three out of the ten selected unique sequences. Altogether 13 promising LAMP assays were identified spanning three unique regions in the closed genome of the onion aster yellows.

Discussion

Molecular detection of phytoplasmas is focused on a few target genes. This presents a limitation for the design of tests for specific detection of ribosomal groups or subgroups and design of tests with very specific requirements for the target sequence as *e.g.* the LAMP. On the other hand, genomic data is becoming more available and can be tapped as a source of potential novel target sequences for test design. Here the coupled use of the RUCS web based pipeline for identification of potential novel target sequences in the publicly available genomes of aster yellows phytoplasmas and the design of specific LAMP assays using PrimerExplorer V5 LAMP primer design is reported. The approach led to the successful identification and quality control based selection of 13 promising LAMP assays spanning three unique regions in the closed genome of the onion aster yellows phytoplasma. While the LAMP assays require experimental testing the approach seems a viable way of increasing the pool of potential target sequences in phytoplasmas. The reliability of this approach however, relies heavily on the completeness and the quality of the genome sequence data. It is expected that additional complete or draft phytoplasma genome sequences will significantly improve the accuracy of the identification of unique sequences common among defined '*Candidatus* Phytoplasma species' or ribosomal groups and subgroups.

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